

Effects of Motivation Strategies for Managing Employees' Retention Rate in Flower Farms in Naivasha Sub-County, Kenya

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Abstract

In the present exceptionally serious work market, there is broad proof that associations paying little heed to measure, innovative advances and market center are confronting maintenance challenges. Individuals are an organization's most basic resources in light of the fact that a remarkable individual gives an organization an upper hand. The purpose of this study was to explore the effect of motivation strategies on employee retention rate in flower farms in Naivasha, Kenya. The research Objectives were; to assess the extent at which progressive career development affects employee retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha; to evaluate the extent at which the financial incentives affect the employee's retention rate; to determine the extent at which the working conditions affects employee's retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha; to establish the extent to which the work policies affect the employee's retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha. The study was anchored on Motivation theories of; Abraham Maslow, Equity theory and McClelland's achievements theory. The study employed a cross-sectional survey design. The study targeted the employees in the various department in the flower farms in Naivasha Sub- County. The total employees of the fifteen farms were 5,001. The sample size for the study was 361 employees from flower firms in Naivasha sub-County. The data was collected through structured questionnaires comprising of closed questions. The Multivariate regression for data analysis was used. The study found that the motivation strategies significantly contributed to employee retention rate with significance level of .000. Progressive career Development had a P value of .024, Financial Incentives scored a P value of .000, whereas Working Conditions managed a P value of .927 and Work Policies had a P value of .030. The study concluded that financial incentives is strongly related with employee retention rate. Therefore, flower firms must focus their attention to financial incentives since it plays a great role towards employee retention rate. The study recommended that the flower companies should be flexible to employees and allow some specific jobs to be done from anywhere. This can be achieved by allowing specific work to be done at home to increase the workers' morale.

Keywords: Motivation Strategies, Employee retention rate, Financial Incentives, Progressive Career Development, Working Conditions, Work Policies

Introduction

At present employee retention is the greatest organization's priority because of increased competition. It is an effective and profitable development towards worker management who are viewed as most noteworthy resources for the organization. Various variables have been ascribed to the expansion in the degree of worker turnover. The maintenance of workers has become a significant test in numerous associations in the 21st Century on account of globalization and numerous different things like innovation and so forth. As indicated by Samuel (2008), globalization has upgraded versatility talented and experienced people in this way quickening the pace of worker turnover in associations. Despite the fact that turnover can be an opportunity for internal promotion as well as for injection of advanced techniques by new workers, it also comes with significant costs both direct and indirect as argued by Dess and Shaw, (2001).

Direct cost includes- replacement, recruitment and selection, training of temporary staff. Indirect costs include pressure inserted on remaining employees, reduced morale, loss of social capital and training costs Armstrong, (2009) maintain that turnover of important labourers could gain unbalanced effect on the organisation. Therefore, in the ever changing world of business today and competition for service delivery surrounding each business, it has become critical retaining experienced and well skilled workers given a

high cost of turnover and the impact caused to the business, Samuel, (2008). Employees leave organizations for many reasons which in many occasions are unknown to their employers, Armstrong, (2009).

Armstrong, (2009) contends that in spite of the fact that cash may itself have no inborn importance, it gains critical spurring power since it comes to symbolize such a large number of impalpable objectives but as per Akintoye (2000), financial incentives stand out to be the most critical way of motivating. Indeed, even among hospital labourers, a few investigations have reflected that low pay rates basically represent work disappointment and movement of such specialists. In conditions like such therefore bettering job satisfaction and endeavors to keep workers require giving higher money related prizes that would make employees see other work less appealing. To oversee great talents, it calls for a steady stabilization linking the human goals and key and money related need of the undertaking. Workers' retention is a system embraced by business to keep up successful workforce and in the meantime meet operational necessities. HR rehearses in a business are utilized for ability securing (enlistment, choice, preparing and improvement, compensate, execution evaluation and so forth). Human asset the executive handles individuals' work place condition and culture in a key way, Mheta et al., (2014).

According to the report of Ministry of Health in Kenya (2009), 90% of employees were satisfied with their jobs it indicated that resources for accomplishing their task were inadequacy and, most indicated that they were dissatisfied with the civil servant's compensation package in relation to other workers outside this job. On the same breathe Mudhune, (2009) argues that allowances, permanent contracts, reduce years of experience before being promoted which nurses have placed the highest attributes values with expectation of monetary enhancement. It is important therefore for managers to identify motivation strategies that would influence employees' decision of leaving the organization so that they stay with the organization for longer period hence influencing retention rate. Retaining a motivated person is a plus to the organization because will help build the business and also reduce recruiting and training costs. Mullins, (2005).

The major challenge associated with motivation strategies in flower farms is high turnover rate where employees were leaving for jobs in other organizations. A loss of employee is a loss of skills knowledge and experienced which has been developed by the company over time. According to Human resource annual labour report (2014), flowers farms within Naivasha between the year 2010 and 2014, yearly labour reports indicated that in a span of 4 years the top management (General Manager's position) was replaced more than twice and on overall there was a turnover of about 5% of a population of 2500 employees and by any standards, this was considered high turnover figure from a unit in a Flower farm and was a source of concern to the entire management team, the Human resources Managers, Production managers and their assistants.

Research Objectives

- i. To assess the effects of progressive career development for managing employee retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha.
- ii. To evaluate the effects of financial incentives for managing employee retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha.
- iii. To determine the effects of working conditions for managing employee retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha.
- iv. To establish the effects of work policies for managing employee's retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha.

Literature Review

The study is anchored on three theories: First, Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory. Abraham Maslow theory is one the most quoted motivation theory that he initiated in 1943 Van Niekerk, (2007). The fundamental truth of this theory is that persons are propelled by their pursuit to satisfy their necessities, or inadequacies that might be classified in five divisions, thus the necessities transpire in a specific chain of significance, where lower sequence necessities ought to be gratified a head of those of a higher succession essence Gouws, (2008).

Physiological needs are associated with elemental endurance, for example need for food or water. Safety needs are not limited to physical security and security, yet it includes an individual's trying individual security, for instance, a legitimate work. Social needs imply cooperation, love and social affirmation and sponsorship, however vainglorious necessities incorporate a person's hankering to be respected by others and without anyone else. Self-acknowledgment occurs at the summit of the necessities levels of leadership, as it addresses a person's trying towards the full improvement of his latent capacity, which is fundamentally never completely accomplished Gouws, (2008). People reliably search after what they don't yet have. Hence, those prerequisites that have recently been satisfied, never again offer inspiration to measures Schultz and Schultz, (2013).

For a long time, minimal empirical proof has been delivered to back up the possibility of a needs hierarchy or the possibility that as requirements are satisfied, their significance reduces Baronetal, (2002). 'Growth' Alderfer emphasized that these necessities don't show up in a chain of command, yet rather on continuity Spector, (2003), furthermore, would in truth be encountered at the same time Alderfer, (2010).

Second, Equity Theory: Stacey Adams formulated the Equity theory in the fact that all people wish to be handled equitably. The Equity Theory is centred along the particulars value, as being handled reasonably in contrast with others as well as inequity where people assume not to be handled approvingly as others. How a person bases whether they are being handled with value or disparity is done as such by concentrating on the person's sources of inputs as well as outputs Baronetal, (2002). 'Growth' Alderfer emphasized that these necessities don't show up in a chain of command, yet rather on continuity Spector, (2003), furthermore, would in truth be encountered at the same time Alderfer, (2010).

Adams (Cited in Martin, 2013) Grant and Shin (2011) plot that one of the key subject in regards to equity theory identifies with how the executive and workers manage disparities that emerge from disparate sorts of correlations. At the point when pay scattering is high, star entertainers causing self-correlations with see high value, yet normal and low entertainers making social examinations may see low value Grant and Shin, (2011).a pay secrecy policy should be implemented to bring a solution to such problems Colella, Paetzold, Zardkoohi, & Wesson (2007).Whereas process theories as examined majorly centre around the event of inspired conduct, the more old style or substance hypotheses manage attempting to discover what components rouses conduct in content theory, Maslow and McClelland give the main needs theories. Equity theory considers remuneration (salary, wage) as an outcome. An outcome is described by Robbins and Judge (2006) as monetary appreciation when an input has been disbursed or spent in kind of operation or utility. Native intelligence could affirm to a common regard, which perspectives pay as a standout amongst the most well-known compensation bundles offered out to beneficiaries, for the most part, labourers on periodical premise. Shoab *et al.*, (2009), see appealing compensation bundle as one of the significant elements of maintaining and turnover since it satisfies both the money related and different materials need of workers

The third theory is McClelland's Achievement Theory: McClelland expressed three kinds of motivational needs under his achievement/needs theory. The need for achievement spurs a person as they intend to accomplish testing objectives and in general movement in one's activity, the need to get input on movement is reliable with inspiration by accomplishment. The requirement for power with an individual is expert persuaded; it reproduces a person's have to control and impact. The requirement for alliance inspires a person by their requirement for social connections and social collaboration. This affiliation powers the craving to be held in high regard among others. The principal part of the achievement or needs theory is that when any of the referenced needs is available in an individual, it has the capacity of rousing conduct and fulfilling said needs Beardwell and Claydon, (2007)

Securing of learning abilities and capabilities is an after effect of instructing of professional or useful aptitudes and information that identify with explicit valuable skills. It frames the centre of apprenticeships and gives the foundation of self-improvement in vocation way. Notwithstanding this essential, training is

required for an exchange, occupation or expert. Eyewitnesses of work advertise, perceive preparing as of the need to keep getting abilities and information past introductory capability to keep up competency and overhaul aptitudes for the duration of working life. Researchers allude to it as expert advancement Gale, (2004).

A number of factors that may lead an employee from either being satisfied or dissatisfied with the job that they do would be the high level of poverty, which may be determined by an individual's level of education or high number of children or dependants. The need to be appreciated in the community and more so in work place where employees spend much of their time is necessary. Social economic status of an individual is mostly determined by the compensation an employee gets from the job he or she does. The tendency of employee high turnover is because of the different reasons, for example, individuals being an contended with sort of work they perform, absence of interests in training and improvement, absence of career training and development call for strategic way of retaining top talent in the organization to realize their job satisfaction in their work related duties and involve them in making of decisions and emboldening their thoughts and aiding to implement as necessary while building their skills through relevant trainings Hay, (2001).

Progressive career development is embraced as key factor to retention. Various studies have indicated Siebert and Zubanov, (2009). Employee learning involves training and development encompassing socialization within the workplace contributes to retention through building employment commitment by show of support. Employees stay for long with an organization due to opportunities such as training and development. Tetley, (2006) detect that progressive career improvement is the core factor which improves adoption of retention strategies. Workers regard education, training and development as important to their total career advancement, motivated to work in a company that offers such opportunity.

According to Seung-Bum Yang *et al*, (2011), financial incentives refer to the amount of wages, salary, and benefits and the individual's perception of their fairness. Studies have discovered that workers who are fairly paid are most likely to be satisfied with their work. Yang noted that if people are more gratified with their wage, therefore the cost of quitting their enterprises is higher; hence, making them develop affirmative stand regarding their career.

Ellickson *et al*, (2002), utilized information from American city workers to look at the impact of pay and advantages on work fulfillment. He found that both fulfillment with pay and fulfillment with benefits have a positive relationship with generally speaking position fulfillment. Monetary impetuses program are intended to motivate representatives dependability and increment profitability among workers. Compensation can be in monetary terms or non-monetary components; it is affected by the employer's strategic remuneration in that what the company offers to employees as compensation/salary package will affect the company recruitment rate, retention rate and employees' satisfaction Bhatnagar, (2007).

Workplace condition is key factor that emerged in any given organization and in relation to productivity. Buhai, Cottini and Westergard-Nielsen, (2008) confirmed that workplace conditions had a significant impact on the performance of an organization. This was based on a cross-sectional survey on the workplace conditions of several Danish farms. Their findings established that good health and safety conditions in the workplace improved the firm's performance because workers were satisfied and more productive at their job. On the other hand, negative health and safety conditions, such as repetitive activities and strenuous jobs, resulted had a negative impact on the farm's performance since workers were less productive due to job-related illness, absenteeism, and job dissatisfaction.

Lopez, (2013) observed that ergonomic work conditions and occupational health and safety affected the productivity of workers in poultry firms. He observed that when employees worked faster and more efficiently when their stations were properly designed, their equipment was adjustable, when lighting and ventilation were adequate, and when access to controls was easy. In addition, the workers felt more confident of their work when they had adequate safety gear such as goggles and boots which prevented the

loss of downtime owing to accidents. Lopez, (2013) also observed that having adequate rest time (such as off days), flexible working hours, defined roles, and recognition of achievement had a great impact on the plant's productivity since workers were less stressed, less prone to burn out and had higher work life quality.

The findings revealed to the researcher that the work environment was not only limited to the physical environment but to organizational elements such as the culture, salary, recognition, and working hours. Sehgal's (2012) article agreed because it identified work environment in the context of the office design, employee health, and corporate culture. The findings were similar in that the author confirmed that a comfortable work environment increased the employee's level of motivation, reduced the error rate, increased the level of innovation, and reduced absenteeism. These behavioural changes had a positive impact on the firm by increasing employee productivity and performance.

Ray, (2013) added that work conditions affected employee attitude, which in turn affected individual productivity in the workplace. To improve the firm's productivity, the author suggested reducing negative employee attitudes caused by lack of trust among heterogeneous workgroups, lack of collaboration, and isolation based on cultural associations. An improvement of negative attitudes, through collaboration and interaction, was seen to have a positive impact on employee behavior. In the readings in this section it is suggested that employers who provided fair and equal work conditions to all workers regardless had higher impact on their productivity compared to those who segregated work conditions based on cultural associations. Organizations cannot exist without effective communication or interactions.

In business conflict management, training becomes so important to executive and staff on how to handle conflicts when differences arise between the individuals in the company. Learning of individuals in a business is exceptionally basic with a point of instigating understanding if differences happen Hammer, (2008).

Preparing and capabilities have been discovered to be correlative, with advanced education connected to an improved probability that a worker will get boss supported preparing. This relationship can be clarified by instructive level being a marker of different aptitudes and capacities that impact both learning capacity and profitability at work. It appears predominantly obvious that a pleased worker is a "better" worker, which is mostly described as a more profitable individual. Nevertheless, several studies having been conducted to verify the affirmative and connection between high job satisfaction and high productivity with nothing convincing are being proven. Analysts have attempted to relate job satisfaction with efficiency, absenteeism, turnover, and other aspects of performance with mixed outcome. Bruce and Blackburn (2009) clarify that Managers and labourers similarly seek after job satisfaction in the regularly guileless conviction that it drives straightforwardly and without a doubt to that other work environment perfect - superior.

Different researchers have carried out countless studies on motivation of employees. In Tehran, Pessaran and Tavakoli, (2011) carried a study on identification of the employees' motivation of Parsian inns in which the following factors were seen as the motivational factors: wage, working condition, safety, status, achievement, recognition, training and improvement, work itself and responsibility. The researcher did not analyse employers' motivation strategies on employee retention there exist a knowledge gap. In Ghana, Owuso, (2012) carried out a study on the effects of motivation on employee performance of commercial bank and the researcher utilized salary, fringed benefits, promotion, and loans as motivating elements. The researcher did not analyse employers' motivation strategies on employee retention there exist a knowledge gap.

In South Africa, Michael (2008) directed research utilizing motivational technique as remedy for worker maintenance and turnover in both government and private business undertakings and the analysts utilized preparing and improvement, acknowledgment, remunerate, a focused pay bundle and employer safety as inspirational elements. Nevertheless, this research was carried out on motivation of workers as well as its effects on employee retention in Ambo mineral water factory. The researcher did not analyze employers' motivation strategies on employee retention there exist a knowledge gap. With the hardships experienced by

supervisors in maintaining their best workers as stated earlier, this study will formulate fundamental research questions that will address the relationship between employers' motivation strategies and employee retention rate in Finlay flowers.

With ambitions and new technology that has created hunger for success and impatient, of young generation employees who might be beginning their working life at the bottom, but does not say they will want low salaries, offers an exciting challenge to entrepreneurs. The employers now need to come up with advanced techniques of recruiting and maintaining great talent since if it continues this way it will open on to greater costs of operating businesses (Kenya institute of management publication 2013/14). As per the 2009 census, 9.4 million persons of the 38.6 million Kenyans are 30 years or less. Kenyan farms are abundantly discovering latest techniques to entice, supervise and maintain the utilities of Generation Y according to the survey, there exists a knowledge gap.

The entrepreneurs should spot expertise from the market, rear and support the newly recruited workers through improving salaries, improving working conditions as well as well-blended young and exposure employees. The major causes leading to constant change of occupations includes the employer attitude and inflexible and unfavourable employment working conditions that employees are subjected to in some companies. Similarly, salary is also dictates whether newly employed staff will last for long at their work stations. The investigation would establish the reason to urgently act on the nervousness of the just recruited workers by telling them the benefits of sticking to one work opportunity and allowing them leeway to grow their creativity for a certain period of time.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design, it was conducted at Naivasha sub-county in Nakuru County. Nakuru County is around 90 km from Nairobi city. Nakuru is rich in agriculture and is with different tourist attraction centres including craters and lakes. The County occupies an area of 7496.5 square kilometres, and Naivasha sub-county Located about 90km from north-west of Nairobi, Naivasha is a popular destination, and horticulture is the principal economic activity of the town.

The target population of the study was 5001 employees from fifteen flower farms in Naivasha sub-county (Kenya Flower Council, 2017). Researchers used the employees as the unit of analysis because they fit well as par the study objectives. The target population per flower farm is summarized in the table below.

Table 1: Target Population

Name of company	Target population
Agribio (K) Ltd	200
Beauty Line Ltd	400
Bigot Flowers Ltd	350
Bilashaka Flowers Ltd	250
Carzan Flowers Ltd	300
De Ruiters (AE) Ltd	450
Florensis (K) Ltd	300
Kongoni River	350
Maridadi flowers Ltd	350
Nini flowers Ltd	400
Oserian Development Co. Ltd	450
Plantation Plants Ltd	300
Van Den Berg (K) Ltd	150
Wildfire Ltd	450
Oinjowa	301
Total	5001

Source: Kenya Flower Council, 2017

The fifteen flower farms were used to determine the sample size. The total employees of the fifteen farms were 5001. The sample size for the study was 361 employees from flower firms in Naivasha sub-

County. The sample size of 361 was determined based on Crecjie and Morgan table (1970). Further stratified proportionate sampling was employed where numbers of employees in each of the department were identified and their sum was used as part or proportion of the whole universe that was sampled. The production department, post-harvest department, Technical department, Administration department of each flower farm were used in the sample size. Within each stratum, a simple random was further employed to come up with a definite sample size.

Table 2: Sampling and Sample Size

Name of company	Target population	Sample Size
Agribio (K) Ltd	200	14
Beauty Line Ltd	400	29
Bigot Flowers Ltd	350	25
Bilashaka Flowers Ltd	250	19
Carzan Flowers Ltd	300	22
De Ruiters (AE) Ltd	450	32
Florensis (K) Ltd	300	22
Kongoni River	350	25
Maridadi flowers Ltd	350	25
Nini flowers Ltd	400	29
Oserian Development Co. Ltd	450	32
Plantation Plants Ltd	300	22
Van Den Berg (K) Ltd	150	11
Wildfire Ltd	450	32
Oinjowa	301	22
Total	5001	361

Source: Researchers, 2021

Questionnaires were the main tool used to collect data. Majorly, closed questionnaires were administered to employees of the farm on 'drop and pick-up basis', whereby respondents were given a period of seven days for them to fill in the questionnaires. Data was analyzed using multivariate linear regression to examine the effectiveness of the independent variables against the dependent variable. The information was presented both qualitatively and quantitatively. Hence, the analytical tool used was as follows;

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \varepsilon$$

Where;

- y – Employee retention rate
- β_0 - Constant variable
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ -Regression coefficients
- X_1 – Progressive career development
- X_2 –Financial incentives
- X_3 – Working conditions
- X_4 - Work policies
- ε = Error term

Data Analysis and Presentation

Multivariate Linear Regression analysis was conducted to predict the outcome on the effect of motivation strategies on employee retention rate of the flower firms in Naivasha Sub-County. The results revealed a positive strong relationship between independent variables (progressive career development, financial incentives, working conditions and work policies) and dependent variable (employee retention rate) as indicated by the R value of 0.722. A coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.521$; this can be translated to mean that progressive career development, financial incentives, working conditions and work policies explained

52.1 % of the variation on employee retention rate, while 47.9 % was explained by other factors outside this study. This is to inform that strategic managers in organizations not to ignore other factors that have not been studied; as they also contribute to the motivation of the employees significantly.

Table 3: Regression Model Summary Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.722 ^a	.521	.517	.27872

Source: Research Data (2021)

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was computed to test the fitness of regression model and the significance level, where F value of 27.748 with P value=0.000 was obtained as shown, which is within the significance level of 0.05. This predicted a strong correlation between the independent variables and dependent variable. This therefore means that the regression model obtained was fit and can be deemed fit for prediction purposes.

Table 4: The ANOVA Results

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.552	4	2.144	27.748	.000 ^b
	Residual	7.352	96	.076		
	Total	15.904	100			

Source: Research Data (2021)

Table 5: Coefficients Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.413	.150		9.363	.000
Progressive career Development	.482	.035	.212	2.139	.024
Financial Incentives	.256	.059	.443	4.033	.000
Working Conditions	-.004	.032	-.008	-.078	.927
Work Policies	.135	.046	.189	2.201	.030

Source: Research Data (2021)

The coefficients analysis revealed that progressive career development had a P=.024, which within the significance level of .050. This implies a strong positive correlation to the dependent variable. Financial incentives had a P=.000, which connotes a strong positive relationship with employee retention rate in flower firms in Naivasha. Working conditions scored a P=.927, which was above the range of significance level of .050, signifying a positive weak relationship with the dependent variable. Lastly, work policies had a P=.030 implying a strong positive relationship with the dependent variable.

As per the variable coefficients results generated therefore, the earlier multiple linear regression for the study was;

$$y=f(\beta_0 + \beta_1x_1+ \beta_2x_2+ \beta_3x_3+ \beta_4x_4+\epsilon)$$

The model, therefore, for the study will now appear as below;

$$y=0.482+ 0.256- 0.004+0.135$$

This is a clear indication that out of the four motivation strategies studied, three of them strongly affect the employee retention rate in flower firms in Naivasha Sub-county. Therefore, it is upon the management of the flower firms to ensure that they improve on these strategic factors in their strategic planning so that can assist in the enhancing of their service delivery. An advice is however, given to the management of the flower firms not to blindly stick to only these four factors studied, of course there are myriad of factors that complement each other in the employee retention rate; and thus, should not be ignored in the process of retaining the workforce, such as employee involvement in decision making process among others.

Discussion of Results

The study findings revealed that motivation strategies strongly affect the employee retention rate among flower firms in Naivasha Sub-County. In as far as the effect of progressive career development on the

employee retention rate is concerned; the findings are in agreement with Siebert and Zubanov, (2009) who remarked that progressive career development is embraced as key factor to retention. He further posits that employees stay for long with an organization due to opportunities such as training and development. Further afield, Tetey, (2006) detects that progressive career improvement is the core factor which improves adoption of retention strategies. Workers regard education, training and development as important to their total career advancement, motivated to work in a company that offers such opportunity. This therefore, shows that organizations need to invest more on their workforce to reciprocate for higher productivity.

On the effect of financial incentives on the employee retention rate the study findings are echoed by Seung-Bum Yang *et al*, (2011), who assert that workers who are fairly paid are most likely to be satisfied with their work. Yang noted that if people are more gratified with their wage, therefore the cost of quitting their enterprises is higher; hence, making them develop affirmative stand regarding their career. Similarly, Ellickson *et al*, (2002), found that both fulfillment with pay and fulfillment with benefits have a positive relationship with generally speaking position fulfillment. On the same note, Bhatnagar, (2007) lauds that Compensation can be in monetary terms or non-monetary components; it is affected by the employer's strategic remuneration in that what the company offers to employees as compensation/salary package will affect the company recruitment rate, retention rate and employees' satisfaction. This implies that proper financial incentive programs have a strategic role on employee retention rate in any organization. Further this suggests that unhappy employees will not focus on the customers as they are supposed to.

In as far as the effect of working conditions on the employee retention rate are concerned the findings are supported by Buhai *et al*, (2008) who confirmed that workplace conditions had a significant impact on the performance of an organization. They argue that good health and safety conditions in the workplace improve the firm's performance because workers become satisfied and more productive at their job. On the other hand, negative health and safety conditions have a negative impact on the firm's performance since workers become less productive due to job-related illness, absenteeism, and job dissatisfaction. Lopez, (2013) also concurs by alluding that ergonomic work conditions and occupational health and safety affect the productivity of workers in poultry firms. He further remarks that having adequate rest time (such as off days), flexible working hours, defined roles, and recognition of achievement have a great impact on the plant's productivity since workers become less stressed, less prone to burn-out and have higher work life quality. Same view is being held by Sehgal's (2012) and Ray, (2013).

Finally, on the effect of work policies on employee retention rate findings are being supported by Bruce and Blackburn (2009) who argue that work retention policies strengthen the capacity of company to attract and retain their employees. This means policies should be in place to provide guidance and direction in the smooth operations of the organizations. In order to enhance employee retention rate in any given organization, it is in order to practice these motivation strategies and many more that have not been studied.

Conclusion

As per the objectives of the study, it is concluded that there was a significant positive relationship between progressive career development, financial incentives and work policies on employee retention rate in flower firms in Naivasha Sub-County. However, a notable weak relationship though positive was revealed on working conditions against the dependent variable. This therefore, postulates that firms need to be careful with kind of work conditions they put in place as they engage their employees. This is so because any caring firm, invest heavily on its human resource.

Recommendations

The study's first objective was to assess the effects of progressive career development for managing employee retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha. The study recommends that flower firms should put in place well designed training and development programs geared towards workforce enrichment.

The second objective was to evaluate the effects of financial incentives for managing employee retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha. A few employees enjoyed a number of bonuses rewards provided by the flower companies based on market rate survey. The study advised that standard bonuses and rewards should be provided to all employees who deserve them in order to motivate them accordingly.

The third objective was to determine the effects of working conditions for managing employee retention rate at flower farms in Naivasha. It implies that working conditions should be designed in a manner that they will control employee turn-over and instead improve on employee retention rate in the firms.

The study further recommends that flower firms should come up with work policies, which are flexible to employees and allow some specific jobs to be done from anywhere. This can be achieved by allowing specific work to be done at home to increase the workers' morale. Especially in this era of Covid-19 Pandemic, flower firms need to be extra cautious not to be super spreaders of the disease amongst themselves.

References

- i. Armstrong, M., and Armstrong, M. (2009). *Armstrong's Handbook of Execution The executives: A Proof Based Manual for Conveying Superior*. London: Kogan
- ii. Beam, L. (2013). *The impact of worker demeanor on efficiency in the working environment*. Recovered from Global Post News.
- iii. Bite, J., and Chan, C.C. (2008). *Human Resource rehearses, Organizational duty and goal to remain*. *Worldwide Journal of Manpower*, 29(6), 503-522.
- iv. Clements-Croome, D.J. (2000). *Making the profitable Workplace*. London: E and FN Spon. Deery, M. (2008). *Ability the board, work-life parity and maintenance methodologies*. 20(7), 23-28.
- v. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2001) *Research strategies in training fifth release* Roughton, Falmers
- vi. Cottrell, T., and Sick. G. (2001). *First mover preferred position and genuine choices*. *Diary of applied Corporate Finance*, 14 (2), 31-41.
- vii. Dess, G. D., and Shaw, J. D. (2001). *Willful turnover, social capital and hierarchical execution*. 26(3), 446-456.
- viii. Franckeiss, A. (2008). *"Mining the great from the farewells"*. *Human asset the executives' global summary*.
- ix. GauravBagga, (2013). *"Step by step instructions to Keep the ability overview, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 3-4*.
- x. Hazard M (1995) *Social Science Research Methods*. East Africa Educational Publishers. Nairobi, Kenya
- xi. Johnson, G., Scholes, K., and Whittington, R. (2008). *Investigating corporate system*. Harlow, Prentice Hall.
- xii. Kaye, B., and Jordan-Evans, S. (2014). *Love them or lose them: Getting great individuals to remain*.
- xiii. Kynndt, N. G., Dochy, F., &Baert, H. (2010). *"Impact of learning and working atmosphere on the maintenance of skilled representatives"*.
- xiv. Legge, K. (1995). *HRM: manner of speaking, reality and shrouded plans*, in J. Story. *A Critical Text*, London, Routledge.
- xv. Leigh Branham, (2005). *The Seven Concealed Reasons Representatives Leave: How to Perceive the Unobtrusive Signs and Act Before Its Past the point of no return*. AMACOM.
- xvi. Lopez, E. C. (2013). *The effect of work environment condition on efficiency and yield in poultry handling*. Recovered from Poultry International.
- xvii. Maurer, T. J., &Lippstreu, M. (2008). *Who will be focused on an association that offers help for representative turn of events? Diary of Management Development*, 27 (3), 328-347.
- xviii. Michael Hay, (2002). *Techniques for endurance in the war on ability*,
- xix. Michael, S.O. (2008). *Using Persuasive Procedure as Panacea for Representative Maintenance and South Africa*. Pro of Trade Proposal, College of Fortress Rabbit.
- xx. Mudhune Sandra, (2009). *Recognizing approaches to improve nurture enlistment and maintenance in country Kenya: Results of a discrete decision try. Exploring intercessions to address the HR for wellbeing emergency. A utilization of discrete decision tests in Kenya, Thailand and South Africa*.
- xxi. Orodho ,A.J. (2005) *Techniques of composing research proposition and reports in training and sociologies*,
- xxii. Oso, W.Y. &Onen, D. (2009). *An overall manual for composing research proposition and report*. Nairobi: Jomo Kenyatta Foundation.

- xxiii. Pessaran D. &Tavakoli S. (2011). *To recognize the representatives' inspiration of Parsian lodgings" in Tehran, Master theory, University of Lulea.*
- xxiv. Sarah Leidner and Simon M.S. (2013). *"Keeping potential employment containers' feet on ground". Human asset the board worldwide reviews, Vol. 21 No. 1, pp. 31-33.*
- xxv. Slope, C. and Gareth, J. (2012). *Vital Management: An Integrated Approach, tenth version. Cengage Learning.*
- xxvi. Vroom, V. (2007). *Another gander at administrative dynamic. Authoritative elements, 28(4), 82-94.*
- xxvii. Walton, R.E. (2000) *"From control to duty in the working environment", Harvard Business Review, 64(2), 77-84.*